

MODERN MECHANISMS FOR COMBATING CORRUPTION IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION BODIES AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a comprehensive analysis of modern anti-corruption mechanisms in public administration bodies, digital transformation, independent oversight institutions, transparency platforms, and international cooperation. Based on the experience of various countries, the effectiveness of these mechanisms, barriers to implementation, and promising directions are examined. Various forms of corruption are highlighted at the business, household, and high levels, and the importance of combat strategies and legal reforms in international practice is highlighted. It analyzes the ongoing anti-corruption reforms in Uzbekistan, the strengthening of the legislative framework, and the implementation of transparency systems.

Corruption is the abuse of public authority by government officials for personal gain or for the benefit of third parties. It remains one of the most serious problems of public governance worldwide. According to Transparency International, corruption causes more than 2.6 trillion US dollars in economic losses annually on a global scale. Corruption not only inflicts financial damage on the state budget, but also erodes public trust in state institutions, restricts private investment, and undermines the principles of social justice. Therefore, improving anti-corruption mechanisms has become a priority direction in modern public administration.

Although financial losses are among the most visible consequences of corruption, its negative impact is not limited to material damage alone. Corruption weakens the state's ability to achieve economic development and to create a stable system that serves the interests of all citizens. At the same time, strong political will aimed at building transparent and accountable institutions with a solid legal foundation is the most effective tool for curbing corruption and eliminating its adverse consequences. According to the explanatory dictionary of Sergey Ivanovich Ozhegov, "Corruption is defined as the moral degradation of officials, as well as public and political figures in general."

Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" (adopted on January 3, 2017) provides official definitions of three key concepts: corruption, corruption-related offenses, and conflict of interest. ¹Accordingly, corruption is defined as the unlawful use of one's official or service position to obtain material or non-material benefits for personal

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-419 dated January 3, 2017, "On Combating Corruption."

interests or for the benefit of others, as well as the unlawful provision of such benefits. A **conflict of interest** is a situation in which a person's personal interests may influence the performance of their official duties. In such cases, personal interests may contradict the interests of society, the state, or an organization. If such a contradiction has already occurred, it is considered an actual conflict of interest; if there is a possibility of its occurrence, it is considered a potential conflict of interest. In general, three main types of corruption can be distinguished in public administration:

1. Business corruption – arises in relations between the state and business entities.

2. Petty (everyday) corruption – occurs in routine interactions between ordinary citizens and officials.

3. High-level corruption – involves political leaders and representatives of the highest judicial bodies.

In recent decades, the development of information and communication technologies has created fundamentally new opportunities in the fight against corruption. The introduction of e-government systems minimizes the human factor in the provision of public services and significantly reduces opportunities for bribery. The experience of South Korea is a vivid example: the implementation of the “e-Procurement” system reduced corruption in public procurement by 87%. Georgia, through digital reforms in the early 2000s², transitioned from being one of the most corrupt countries to becoming relatively transparent. Blockchain technology ensures the immutability of data when applied in land cadastre, healthcare records, and public procurement. Countries such as Honduras and Ghana have significantly reduced corruption related to property rights by transferring land registries to blockchain systems.

As Robert Klitgaard noted:

“Digitalization does not eliminate corruption, but it fundamentally narrows its opportunities when every transaction leaves a trace, there is little room for manipulation.”

In international practice, there are specialized anti-corruption agencies:

STATE / ORGANIZATION YEAR ESTABLISHED

Hong Kong — ICAC	1974
Singapore — CPIB	1952
Latvia — KNAB	2002
Indonesia — KPK	2002
Ukraine — NABU	2015
Albania — SPAK	2019

Indeed, corruption reflects the imperfect nature of human behavior. Some scholars consider excessive bureaucracy and the growing number of officials as its main causes. In Uzbekistan, large-scale reforms are being implemented, including the introduction of modern market mechanisms, reduction of non-core functions in state bodies, digitalization of public administration, and involvement of the private sector in performing certain state functions³.

In order to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of public administration, on April 3, 2021, the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, adopted Resolution No. PQ-5053 “On optimizing the structure of state authorities and reducing staff units.” This resolution

² Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe/OSCE chapter international anti-corruption strategies p. 155-162

³ De Speville, B. Hong Kong: Policy Initiatives Against Corruption. — Paris: OECD, 1997.

предусматривает the optimization of managerial staff by up to 15% and reduction of deputy leadership positions in ministries and agencies. In recent years, Uzbekistan has carried out comprehensive reforms aimed at preventing and combating corruption. Systems for assessing corruption risks in state bodies have been improved, and integrity standards have been introduced. In accordance with Presidential Decree No. 6013, the Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established, tasked with identifying and preventing corruption risks. The platform E-Anticor.uz serves as an information system that collects and reflects data on the effectiveness of anti-corruption efforts. Through this portal, users can access data on the dynamics of anti-corruption measures since 2022, annual rankings, as well as registers of positions and relationships most vulnerable to corruption.

Conclusion: One of the key characteristics of corruption is its hidden and mutually beneficial nature. In many cases, corrupt activities remain undisclosed and unreported because the parties involved benefit from them. For example, an official may provide legal or illegal services to a citizen or entrepreneur in exchange for a bribe. As a result, both parties perceive benefits and attempt to conceal the act. Therefore, many countries face systemic difficulties in addressing this issue. The most important factor in combating corruption is not law, but **will**. Laws can be adopted, institutions established, and technologies introduced; however, without genuine political will and societal commitment, these measures remain merely formal. For sustainable results, intolerance toward corruption must become a social norm and a fundamental value.

References:

- 1.Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-419 dated January 3, 2017, "On Combating Corruption."
- 2.Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe/OSCE chapter international anti-corruption strategies p. 155-162
- 3.International Monetary Funds article, Противодействия в коррупции в сфере государственного управление, Витор Гаспар, Паоло Мауро и Пауло Медас, 2019/04/04
- 4.Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5053 "On optimizing the structure and reducing the number of staff units of state authorities and administration."
- 5.De Speville, B. Hong Kong: Policy Initiatives Against Corruption. — Paris: OECD, 1997.
- 6.Heywood, P. Routledge Handbook of Political Corruption. — London: Routledge, 2015